

Schrödinger used Schrödinger's cat thought experiment to argue the problem existing in [Copenhagen interpretation](#). Schrödinger's cat thought experiment looks like a reasonable questioning. And [Copenhagen interpretation](#) can not answer the Schrödinger's argument, either. But in fact, cat is not an appropriate example as an object for this thought experiment.

The interpretation as follows,

1. Cat and photon (or electron) should be categorized to two different types.

Cat can be recognized as an existence in macro material world. But photon (or electron) is an existence in the subatomic world. Essentially, the macro material world can not be easily understood as piling up the existence in the subatomic world.

2. The cat state is certain when it is observed at any given time t . It is either alive or dead.

3. Human observation can not influence cat's life or death.

4. Different people will get the same observation result at the same time t , except that human observation can influence the atom decaying.

5. Cat is not an appropriate example for the experiment object. It just makes people confused. Because cat can not be in superposition state of live and death. At any given time t , cat is either alive or dead.

The real superposition state means mixture of multiple states at any given time. The object state will be fixed and will be one of the multiple states just when the object is observed.

If there is no atom decay trigger poison mechanism in the box, human can almost assure the cat being alive. Because of the atom decay trigger poison mechanism, before opening the box, human have to hypothesize that the cat is either alive or dead. So the probability for each is 50%. This is reasoned from probability aspect. But this does not mean superpositionality of cat state.

6. Observation from observer : equipment or equipment+human or human. This experiment ,the observation is just from observer human.

7. Because cat has no superposition state. Observer human can not influence cat's life or death. And then observer effect does not exist in this experiment.

Above all, cat is not an appropriate example as an object in Schrödinger's thought experiment.

Note: Observer effect was somewhat disproved by probability of measurement outcome in quantum physics.

But an argument can be that probabilistic measurement outcome is not a strong evidence to disprove observer effect. In macro material world, one thousand inspectors measure the same object with the same ruler but need to respectively estimate the number below the minimum scale or with other tools by predefined measuring procedure. The one thousand measurements will also very likely be probabilistic.